

Development of a method to identify spatial variation in onion crop development and predict yield

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Abstract

Background: Many factors add to variability and limit the profitability of onion production. Precision management could add value but requires timely capture and processing of crop development data and prediction of yield to inform management decisions. We assessed onion canopies with a range of sensors and sought correlations with yield data. We report results from satellite NDVI and smartphone app percentage canopy cover.

Methods: Mid-season World View 2 imagery at about 5 – 7 leaf stage was processed and paddock NDVI maps prepared. Areas of high, medium and low canopy were identified and relative yields determined at commercial maturity in February. NDVI and yield were compared.

The smartphone app was used to survey a 1 ha crop and canopy cover maps prepared. In parallel, 1m² plots were photographed at 3, 5, 7 leaf and bulbing, images processed to determine canopy cover. Percentage cover was compared to destructive leaf area and fresh mass measurements.

Results: Strong correlations were found between NDVI and yield which enabled the retrospective creation yield and profit maps, useful for review but not current season management.

Very strong relationships were found between processed smartphone images and measurements of fresh mass and leaf area index.

Discussion: Satellite imagery is expensive at paddock scale, hard to obtain and slow to become available to the manager. However there does seem to be a relationship between early season canopy and harvest yield.

Smartphone imagery can be cheaply gathered and immediately available. The relationship between ground cover and leaf area index suggests potential to create predictive yield maps that may inform current season management such as variable rate fertiliser.

Conclusion: Significant progress has been made, but the considerable variability in onions continues to provide challenges.

The Onions NZ Sustainable Farming Fund project “Enhancing the profitability and Value of New Zealand onions” seeks to identify variation and causes within crops of onions. This work is a collaboration with Plant and Food Research. LandWISE’s role is to identify tools and procedures to assess crop variability at field scale to provide information for improved decision making.

Several commonly used reflectance sensors were used to assess canopy size and “greenness”. All the sensors used were able to capture data to create spatial difference maps, and through comparison of successive measurement can show temporal variations. The architecture of the onion plant, a fine vertically oriented plant, made early measurement difficult. NDVI maps created at early stages are strongly influenced by base soil reflectance masking some crop variation.

Additionally smartphone image analysis applications *ELA Free*, *Canopeo* and *ASL CoverMap* were used to determine canopy ground cover. These field measurements were compared against detailed plot assessments made by Plant and Food Research in a parallel monitoring exercise.

The ground cover assessed by processed phone images correlated very strongly with laboratory fresh mass and leaf area index measurements. There is little difference between the results of ground cover assessed by the three smartphone apps if correctly calibrated.

An iPhone 6+ with *ASL CoverMap* software was mounted on a tractor and connected to high accuracy GPS. This application recorded GPS position and percentage greenness being shown in each frame captured. The data were converted using ArcGIS into an interpolated map of the whole field. The map was used as a base against which final hand harvest yield data were compared, and the resulting relationship used to prepare an equivalent yield map.

We have developed a decision support concept of Management Action Zones (MAZ). Zones are defined on the basis of canopy limitations caused by population and/or plant growth.

In essence the MAZ process involves:

Selecting paddock zones

1. Setting sample plots
2. Counting plants
3. Taking photos
4. Converting images to percentage Canopy Cover
5. Loading into website that does maths and produces reports
6. Determining a suitable management response, whether tactical or strategic.

Three main areas at the LandWISE MicroFarm were identified based on number of preceding onion crops (zero or two) and cover crop history (oats, mustard or pasture). In addition we deliberately applied heavy irrigation to part of each area to simulate rainfall at emergence. This gave six different MAZs.

Because onions are extremely variable, we established 15 bed-width plots in each MAZ and monitored them through the season. Population was counted and photographs taken at 3 leaf, 5 leaf and bulbing. These were processed using the *Canopeo* application to determine the percentage of green pixels, which we used as a measure of crop canopy cover. Actual yield was determined at harvest for each plot.

We developed an online calculator, *SmartFarm* which uses algorithms to analyse the data, compare current against expected canopy size, report predicted yields and define Management Action Zone categories.

The whole crop was also surveyed at bulbing using *ASL CoverMap*, and a canopy cover map produced. This suggested alternative zoning patterns based on actual rather than anticipated areas of difference. We believe a whole paddock map created at 3 leaf is feasible and will provide useful information in time for in-season management responses.

Actual yield data obtained from each plot at harvest was related to the *ASL CoverMap* made at bulbing and a function found to convert the canopy cover at bulbing to actual yield measured at harvest. The total predicted paddock yield was in line with earlier grower estimates and matched the tonnes sent to the packhouse.

With the yield map as a base, we analysed the impact and apparent cost of poor irrigation and poor drainage. This supported decisions to extend our irrigator and undertake land shaping to improve drainage.

We have also noted an apparent relationship between canopy cover at bulbing and top down at lifting. We believe that may provide information about crop quality and storage potential. This will be further explored.

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